

11th ISAJ Annual Symposium 2020 (Web)

Innovations in Science and Technology for New Issues and Challenges

Abstracts

December 4th, 2020

Zoom Platform

Contents

1-2 Program

3-8 Special Interest Session: COVID-19 Pandemic

Plenary and Invited Talks

9-13 #A1

14-18 #B1

19-23 #C1

Plenary and Invited Talks

24-28 #A2

29-32 #B2

33-38 #C2

Young Researchers' Session

39-47 #A3

48-55 #B3

56-63 #C3

Japan Standard Time (JST)				
9:00-10:30	Inaugural Session (Zoom ID - 818 6634 9822, PW- 083746)			
9:00 - 9:05	Welcome Address	Symposium Conveners		
9:05 - 9:10	Welcome Address	Sunil Kaul, Chairman, ISAJ		
9:10 - 9:25	Inaugural Address	H.E. Mr. Sanjay Kumar Verma, Ambassador of India to Japan		
9:25 - 10:00	Keynote Lecture	Masaru Hori, Director, cLPS, Nagoya University - Plasma Sciences towards Global Innovations		
10:00 - 10:10	Special Address	Usha Dixit, Counsellor (S&T), Embassy of India - Science and Technology Initiatives in India		
10:10 - 10:25	Special Address	B.S. Murty, Director, IIT Hyderabad - Synergistic growth through Collaboration		
10:25 - 10:30	Vote of Thanks	Alok Singh, Vice-Chairman, ISAJ		
Break				
10:30 - 10:40				
10:40 - 12:15	Special Interest Session: COVID-19 Pandemic (Zoom ID - 818 6634 9822, PW- 083746) Chair: Manjiri Kulkarni-Deshpande			
10:40 - 11:10	Distinguished Lecture	COVID-19: Immunological mechanisms, cytokine storm, asthma and allergies Ruby Pawankar, Nippon Medical School Tokyo		
11:10 - 11:25	Invited Talk#1	SARS-CoV-2 and human body: perspectives from its genetics, diagnostics to therapeutics Santosh Gothwal, Kyoto University		
11:25 - 11:45	Plenary Talk	Role of ashwagandha in stress, health and COVID-19 management Renu Wadhawa, National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science & Technology (AIST)		
11:45 - 12:00	Invited Talk#2	A Monologue with solitude & 'transience' during the pandemic Jhuma Basak, International Psychoanalytical Association, (IPA) London		
12:00 - 12:15	Invited Talk#3	Rise of AI-powered video analytics for society transformation in the times of global pandemic Saichandra Teja, CKM VIGIL Pvt. Ltd.		
Lunch				
12:15-13:10				
Plenary and Invited Talks				
13:10-14:30		Parallel Session #A1 (Zoom ID - 956 5153 4639, PW- Ymrds0)	Parallel Session #B1 (Zoom ID - 818 6634 9822, PW- 083746)	Parallel Session #C1 (Zoom ID - 954 7245 7318, PW- Z1Q4gp)
		Industrial and Technological Innovation Chair: Kuldeep Saxena & Prerna Joshi	Human Health and Safety Chair: Tanima Biswas & Santosh Gothwal	Energy and Environment Chair: Frank Wilson
13:10-13:30	Plenary Talk#1	Kotaro Kataoka, IIT H & Keio University	Advanced nano theragnostics to cure cancer D. Sakthi Kumar, Toyo University	Combinatorial method for new materials design Suhas R. Dey, IIT Hyderabad
13:30-13:45	Invited Talk#1	Crafting multimetallic magnetic-plasmonic nanoparticles Priyank Mohan, JAIST	On biophysical interaction involving proteins and indole drugs originated from north east indian biodiversity Jhimli Bhattacharya, NIT Nagaland	Diboron-catalyzed dehydrative amidation of aromatic carboxylic acids with amines Dattatraya B. Bagal, Nagoya University
13:45-14:00	Invited Talk#2	Urban planning in light of technological singularity Shreyas Bharule, UoT, ADBI	Some new insights into chromatin organization using statistical physics S.S. Ashwin, Nagoya University	Nano-inclusion in thermoelectric AZO thin films Shrikant Saini, Kyushu Institute of Technology
14:00-14:15	Invited Talk#3	Wavelength tunable plasmonic nanostructures for sensing Bikas Ranjan, NIMS	Importance of plant nutraceuticals for human health Suhas Karkute, Indian Institute of Vegetable Research	Plasma-enhanced CVD growth of vertically oriented carbon nanowalls and its characteristics Dennis Christy Peterraj, Nagoya University
14:15-14:30	Invited Talk#4	Influence of structure and processing methodologies on properties of polymeric materials Sreenivas Kummara, Toyota Tech. Institute	Cucurbitacin-B exhibits anticancer activity in a mutated p53 isoform harbouring tongue carcinoma HSC3 cells Sukant Garg, AIST Tsukuba	Functional substrate for tuning the electronic structure of IrO₂ nanoparticles for efficient water electrolysis Rajashekar Badam, JAIST
14:30-14:40	Break			

Plenary and Invited Talks				
14:40-16:00		Parallel Session #A2 (Zoom ID - 956 5153 4639, PW- Ymrds0)	Parallel Session #B2 (Zoom ID - 818 6634 9822, PW- 083746)	Parallel Session #C2 (Zoom ID - 954 7245 7318, PW- Z1Q4gp)
		Industrial and Technological Innovation Chair: Prerna Joshi	Human Health and Safety Chair: Santosh Gothwal	Energy and Environment Chair: Frank Wilson & Kuldeep Saxena
14:40-15:00	Plenary Talk#2	Painless microneedle mimicking female mosquito based on microneedle production technique Kazuyoshi Tsuchiya, Tokai University	Biological and medical applications of raman spectroscopy Hemant Noothalapati, Shimane University	Smart windows for energy savings utilizing vanadium dioxide films with insulator-metal transition Kunio Okimura, Tokai University
15:00-15:15	Invited Talk#5	Fatigue-corrosion behavior of Zr55Al10Cu30Ni5 bulk metallic glass in distilled water Benjamin Guennec, University of Toyama	Multi-color regulation of gold (I) NHC co-ordination polymer by external stimuli: via molecular aggregates Satya Arruri, Ritsumeikan University	Spatial distribution of brick kilns revealed by remote sensing: transfer learning based detection around delhi Prakhar Mishra, RIHN, Kyoto
15:15-15:30	Invited Talk#6	Charge density analysis of p-hole interactions of acid dimers in a new co-crystal hydrate of gallic acid and pyrazine : application of quantum crystallography Rumpa Pal, University of Tsukuba	Insights into CRISPR/Cas9 system as a genome editing tool Jaspreet Kaur Dhanjal, AIST	Fabrication of highly abundant and cost-effective Fe2O3 nanostructures for effective electrocatalytic water splitting Sivaranjani Arumugam, Nagoya University
15:30-15:45	Invited Talk#7	Development of polyaniline based conducting polymer nano composite for flexible electronics applications Divya Anand, Nippon Paint Holdings Co Ltd	An integrative computational systems biology analysis of lung gene expression profiles to understand the differential roles of Tetraspanins Cd151 and Cd9 in lung fibrosis and emphysema Lokesh Tripathi, ArChER Osaka	Flexible thermoelectric material for energy applications Saurabh Singh, Toyota Technological Institute
15:45-16:00	Invited Talk#8	Recent advancements in chemical/bio sensors Ganesh Kumar Mani, Tokai University		Fabrication of hollow germanium spheres by dropping method Kunal Bhagat, Ritsumeikan University
16:00-16:15 Break				
16:15-17:35 Young Researchers' Session				
16:15-17:35		Parallel Session #A3 (Zoom ID - 956 5153 4639, PW- Ymrds0)	Parallel Session #B3 (Zoom ID - 818 6634 9822, PW- 083746)	Parallel Session #C3 (Zoom ID - 954 7245 7318, PW- Z1Q4gp)
		Industrial and Technological Innovation Chair: Sharath Srinivasamurty & Pankaj Sahlot	Human Health and Safety Chair: S. S. Ashwin & Santosh Gothwal	Energy and Environment Chair: Elango Chandiran & Karre Rajamallu
16:15-16:25	YR #1	Comparative corrosion behavior of harmonic structured high entropy cantor alloy, maraging steel and SUS304L Debdipta Banik, IIT Kanpur, India	Fucoxanthin exerts anti-stress activities and is suitable for recruitment for the improvement of the quality of life Sajal Afzal, AIST	Comparative analysis of sand indices for monitoring of soiling on solar farms in arid environments Hitesh Supe, Hokkaido University
16:25-16:35	YR #2	Modeling of soft actuators to grasp food items for lunch box packaging Sachin Yadav, Ritsumeikan University	Novel caffeic acid phenethyl ester-mortalin antibody nanoparticles offer enhanced selective cytotoxicity to cancer cells Jia Wang, AIST	Monitoring of ravines and gully erosion using remote sensing and GIS in last few decades: Review Raveena Raj, Hokkaido University
16:35-16:45	YR #3	An efficient approach to zero crossing detection based on opto-coupler Ankita Gupta, Hokkaido University	Withaferin A and CAPE combination for treatment for aggressive cancers Anissa Nofita Sari, AIST	Synergistic use of aerial and ground survey techniques for archaeological site mapping Stanley Anak Suab, Hokkaido University
16:45-16:55	YR #4	Cellulose nanofiber reinforced starch film with high mechanical strength and durability in water Raghav Soni, Osaka University	Stem extract of cinnamomum zeylanicum cause cytotoxicity in the osteosarcoma cells He Huifu, AIST	Evaluation of anticancer activities in medicinal mushroom (Cordyceps militaris) grown on fluorinated medium Xiaoshuai Li, Tsukuba University
16:55-17:05	YR #5	Monitoring human behavior using pose estimation Aditya Singh Rathore, Ritsumeikan University	Lipoic acid enantiomers exert hypoxia and anti-stress activity in mammalian cells and cause lifespan extension in human lung fibroblasts Ashish Kaul, AIST	Development of vitamin D3 and its analogs for prevention and treatment of osteoporosis and cancer H. Oshita, Toyama Prefectural University
17:05-17:15	YR #6	Three-arm aerial manipulator system (TAMS) for UAVs to realize multiple tasks Hannibal Paul, Ritsumeikan University	A multi-target novel small molecule as an alternative therapeutic strategy for the luminal-A breast cancers Ahmed Elwakeel, AIST	Development of recombinant adenoviral vectors for the treatment of rickets Satoko Kise, Toyama Prefectural University
17:15-17:25	YR #7	Interface analysis of γ -CuI and β -Ga2O3 heterojunction by temperature dependent device characteristics Rama Venkata Krishna Rao, Okayama University	Effect of ashwagandha withanolides (withanone and withaferin-A) on muscle cell differentiation Huayue Zhang, AIST	Analysis of the effects of vitamin D and calcium on the female reproductive functions among genetically modified rats Mana Yamaguchi, Toyama Prefectural University
17:25-17:35	YR #8	Electrochemical performance of high phosphorus pig iron as sacrificial anode for cathodic protection of steel in seawater Nisheeth Kr. Prasad, IIT Kanpur, India	Molecular link between cancer and hyperglycemia-intervention by natural compounds Hazna Noor Meidinna, DAILAB-AIST	Photocatalytic marimo balls (P-Marimo) based on plasmonic titanium nitride and chromium-doped titanium dioxide for eco-friendly water treatment Manpreet Kaur, NIMS-Tsukuba
17:35-17:45 Break				
17:45-18:00 Closing Ceremony and Award Session (Zoom ID - 818 6634 9822, PW- 083746)				

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Special Interest Session: COVID-Pandemic

Distinguished Lecture

Cytokine storm in COVID-19—immunopathological mechanisms, clinical characteristics, and therapeutic modalities

Ruby Pawankar, Nippon Medical School Tokyo

Invited Talk #1

SARS-CoV-2 and Human body: perspectives from its Genetics, Diagnostics to Therapeutics

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The pandemic of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) highlights the need to develop effective medicine and proper diagnostic tools to control the recurrent outbreaks on world-wide basis. On current understandings about pathogenesis of SARS-CoV-2, its spike protein is initially bound to human ACE2 mainly expressed on respiratory epithelium, followed by viral proliferation hijacking the host gene regulatory mechanisms. Systemic spread of virus particles from the infected cells on blood stream can lead to damage multiple organs other than lungs perhaps coupled with so-called cytokine-storm machinery. Of note, blood vessels as themselves are so heavily injured as to cause lethal hypercoagulopathic states in severe cases of SARS-CoV-2 infection. Thus, identification of effective management to ameliorate endothelial injury is also in urgent need.

In this presentation, at first, I will give you a general picture of genomic characteristics of SARS-CoV-2 compared to SARS-CoV, which should help you understand biological foundation behind the view that diagnostic methods on antigen-detection for SARS-CoV-2 infection would be less effective than RT-PCR. Then, the rationale behind current strategies for the vaccine development is discussed from my point of view. In the final part, I will briefly introduce a novel clinical trial targeting against hypercoagulopathy, which is currently ongoing in our laboratory.

Plenary Talk

Role of Ashwagandha in stress, health and COVID-19 management

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Ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*: family Solanaceae) is a widely admired herb in traditional Indian home medicine. It has been used for a variety of remedies. However, laboratory evidence and molecular mechanisms of its actions are only beginning to be determined. We initiated search on bioactivities in the leaves of Ashwagandha and found that both alcoholic (i-Extract) and water extracts (WEX) of Ashwagandha leaves possess considerable anticancer activities. Bioactives for anticancer activity were identified as withanolides, withanone (Wi-N) and withaferin-A (Wi-A) in the i-Extract, and triethylene glycol in the WEX. Using multiple experimental and bioinformatics approaches, we demonstrated that the two kinds of extracts possess different bioactive constituents and work through independent pathways against cancer.

The recent outbreak of the novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) in the Wuhan province of China has taken millions of lives world-wide. While new line of drug/vaccine development has been initiated world-wide, in the current scenario of high infected numbers, severity of the disease and high morbidity, repurposing of the existing drugs is heavily explored. We investigated the effect of several natural compounds on host-receptors that are critically involved in viral infection and selected Ashwagandha-derived Withanolides as candidate compounds that downregulated expression of host cell receptors (ACE2 and TMPRSS2) required for viral entry into the host cells. We also used a homology-based structural model of transmembrane protease serine-2 (TMPRSS2) and found that both Wi-A and Wi-N could bind and stably interact at the catalytic site of TMPRSS2. Wi-N showed stronger interactions with TMPRSS2 catalytic residues than Wi-A and was also able to induce changes in its allosteric site. Furthermore, Wi-N, but not Wi-A, interacted with virus protein M^{pro} causing its inhibition and hence blocking the viral replication. In view of these findings, we have developed technologies to obtain Active Ingredients Enriched Ashwagandha by manipulating its environmental conditions. We demonstrate, for the first time, (i) field raised i-Ashwagandha leaves with high proportion of active withanolides as compared to the roots, (ii) hydroponically raised i-Ashwagandha and characterization of its bioactives, and (iii) method of extraction with enriched bioactive components that may serve as an economic drug especially when modern medicine is either not available or limited by severe side effects.

Invited Talk #2

A Monologue with Solitude & ‘Transience’ During the Pandemic

Jhuma Basak, PhD (Psychology)

Psychoanalyst & Member, International Psychoanalytical Association (IPA), London

Member, IPA-Committee on Women & Psychoanalysis

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Abstract:

The pandemic of COVID-19 has not only effected the survival of the human race directly but has equally shaken up the internal psychical sustenance and endurance of humankind. In this bearing one attempts to study from a psychoanalytic lens the role of solitude and mentalization in one’s holistic development, distinguishing from loneliness, as psychic processes that are necessary constituents for the evolution of resilience of the ego against such atrocities of life. It also prompts one to critically read societal structural schemas, like education, that assists in such constitutional cultivation of an individual adult’s integrated formation of cognitive faculties and emotional disposition. Subsequently it leads one to make equanimous choices in life, particularly when confronted with any ‘all-engulfing’ calamity of life, be it political, natural, man-made, individual or communal.

What happens when such structural schemas and compassionate individual affective agencies (in family or society) are unavailable to humankind? Does it drive one to reveal one’s acutely anxious, self-centred, conceited being, with no concern for fellow beings in society? How have women dealt with this lack all along in their various social roles as daughters, sisters, wives, mothers – with or without a pandemic? How have they dealt with their reservoir of “boundless aloneness”, (Bollas, 1989), to negotiate solitude and transience in spite of this lack of containment, aspiring to adult choices of fortitude, expressing higher capacity of resilience against such cataclysm?

In the Japanese child rearing process there is a unique quality called ‘transience’ interwoven in the mother-child dyad. The philosophy of this lies in preparing the growing child equipped for its future adult life and the uncertainties of existential trajectory that awaits one in this world – perhaps a cultural realization of Japan’s incessant exposure to environmental challenges of earthquakes and typhoons for centuries along with aftermaths of wars and regimentation. It is a matter of significance to explore the potential of human agency to internalize this quality of transience in such grave times.

This paper examines these various aspects of human psychological struggle to grapple with the COVID-19 situation, while at the same time aspires to find its adaptability and its capacity to overcome such enormity of a testing time in history.

Invited Talk #3

Rise of AI-powered video analytics for society transformation in the times of global pandemic

Saichandra Teja, CKM VIGIL Pvt. Ltd.

Plenary and Invited Talks

Crafting Multimetallic Magnetic-Plasmonic Nanoparticles

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Tracing since stone age, followed by bronze, iron and steel ages, alloys have been the indispensable part of materials world, owing to their superior and unique properties in contrast to the individual elemental component. In pursuit of creativity, similar trend was adopted by scientific community in the existing era of nanomaterials, towards developing the multi-metallic systems in various structural forms such as an alloy, a core-shell or other integrated multielemental morphologies. However, unfortunately, integration of some elements are challenged by their intrinsic immiscibilities in a bulk system, therefore, limiting the countless interesting possible combinations which could have been generated.

One of such examples, is combination of plasmonic (Au, Ag) and magnetic (Fe) nanomaterials, which if integrated can represent next-generation bioprobes, simultaneously enabling plasmonic bioimaging and magnetic manipulation. Even though much effort has been made to synthesize AuFe alloy¹ or FePt@Au/Ag core@shell² magnetic-plasmonic systems, literature disagreement has been observed for structure-property relation, and therefore, there still remains several challenges regarding the chemical synthesis of homogeneous alloy or core-shell nanoparticles (NPs) without any phase segregation and inability to coat magnetic core with the plasmonic shell, suppressing pure Au/Ag phase as a major challenge. On the other hand, there are a number of studies which show that, Au or Ag has been doped in *fcc* FePt alloy, to lower the annealing temperature required for the transformation from chemically-disordered to ordered phase.³ Getting inspired from previous literature, a synthetic strategy was framed where Pt was employed as a mediating element for combining Fe with Au or Ag, to form Au_xFe_yPt_{100-x-y} or Ag_xFe_yPt_{100-x-y} ternary NPs systems.⁴ Through studies, it was confirmed that Pt plays a critical role in the formation of ternary metallic NPs, and that the magnetic and plasmonic properties dependent primarily on the final structure and composition. This talk hence, will be focused on presenting new avenue to develop magnetic-plasmonic NPs and to give insight into the creation of multielement nanocrystals that are typically immiscible.

Keywords: Multimetallic NPs, LSPR, Superparamagnetism, Inorganic Nanomaterials.

1) V. Amendola *et al.*, *Nanoscale* **2013**, 5, 5611. 2) K. Yano *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2009**, 113, 13088. 3) S. Kinge *et al.*, *Nano Lett.* **2009**, 9, 32. 4) P. Mohan *et al.*, *Langmuir* **2017**, 33, 7, 1687.

Urban Planning in light of Technological Singularity

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In physics, a singularity is a point in space and time where the mathematics of arriving at an explanation breaks and human capacity to comprehend terminates too. Keeping this analogy, a singularity in the chronology of human development would occur if the growth in technological progress bring massive changes in the ways social affairs as we know them today will come to an end. At such a point, the authorities, institutions, economy would not survive in its current state and form, neither will social values be the same. Several authors, researchers, and scientists confidently predict that humanity will arrive at the technological singularity point by the mid-21st century, and it will occur in two areas - Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Neurotech. However, discussions on how such a transformation to the basic building block of societies will affect the cities and their planning remain unexplored. Keeping in mind the technologically induced social transformations as experienced in the times of the pandemic, this presentation discusses the challenge of urban planning considering technological singularity.

Wavelength tunable plasmonic nanostructures for sensing
Bikas Ranjan, NIMS

Influence of Structure and Processing Methodologies on Properties of Polymeric Materials

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Theoretical and experimental investigations on the structure and property relationship of various advanced polymeric materials are very essential. These studies can give us concrete knowledge on developing new methodologies to understand via hierarchical levels which can allow us to generate new insights for enhancing performance and increase the applications of the particular polymer. Some of them are homopolymers, copolymers including block-copolymers and their self-assembly, blends and nanocomposites. In the present research, I briefly present how the structure and processing methodologies can influence the final properties and respective structural evolution phenomenon of engineering polymer materials.

Advanced Nano Theragnostics to Cure Cancer

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Fusion of Nanotechnology and Biotechnology lead to the new research field known as “Theragnostics”. New nano formulations are developed under this field to diagnosis and for the treatment of the cancer. New targeting techniques are used so that the nano theragnostics materials can selectively kill only the cancer cells by sparing the normal cells. We have developed many nano formulations, which are very useful against different cancers such as Breast cancer, Pancreatic cancer and Brain tumor etc. We found that the formulations which we had developed can successfully cross the blood brain barrier and deliver the drugs at sites in the case of Brain tumor treatment.

Will be presenting our latest results based on different formulations, which we had developed under theragnositcs materials.

Biophysical Analyses of Traditional Medicinal Plant Derived Tribal Medicines of Nagaland and North-eastern India

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Nagaland, the land of festivals, is one of the most important state among the 'seven-sisters' of North-Eastern (NE) India. This province is well-known for its diverse population of people with unique ethnic, tribal background, culture, healthy lifestyle, traditional medicinal plants, herbal drugs etc,. Starting from a detailed documentation of such medicinal plant based drugs in this study, we have also reported the biophysical analyses of some of those tribal medicines. Various alkaloids (specially indoles) are abundantly present in those plants with wide-spread pharmaceutical applications towards gastritis, hypertension, diabetes, cancer, infertility etc. Despite of the popularity and usage of traditional plant based natural drugs, the scientific background behind their effectiveness, mechanism of action are yet unexplored. Different biophysical tools like UV-Vis spectroscopy, fluorescence, IR-spectroscopy, circular dichroism, calorimetry and molecular docking have been used for the said purpose. The interaction studies portrayed a significant degree of specificity and high affinity of the ligands towards DNAs and proteins. A detailed report of the binding constants, binding stoichiometries under different temperature and salt conditions and associated thermodynamics/energetics have been presented here. This research project has multifaceted application including understanding the drug action and development of rational therapeutic agents from natural sources.

This work is joint with Dr. Souvik Maiti, Senior Principle Scientist, CSIR-Institute of Genomics and Integrative Biology, New Delhi and Mr. Soching Luikham and Ms. Vibizenuo Rupre-O, Ph.D Research Scholars, Department of Chemistry, National Institute of Technology Nagaland, Dimapur.

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Some new insights into chromatin organization using statistical physics.

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Chromatin organization and dynamics are critical to the understanding of genomic functioning. Super-resolution microscopy has made it possible to investigate the motion of the chromatin in live cells. A live cell is very “noisy.” Noise from experimental data needs to be eliminated to get reasonable insight. We applied methods of statistical physics to single nucleosome trajectories from live cells, which helps us penetrate through some of this noise to gain understanding. Further, we perturb the cell and observe variations in statistical quantities to infer the underlying dynamic organization.

Importance of plant nutraceuticals for human health

Suhas Gorakh karkute¹, Tanmay Kumar Koley², Kaushik Banerjee³

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Good health is highly important for survival of the human race. The covid-19 pandemic has further stressed on this aspect for boosting the immunity. The humans with strong immunity are less likely susceptible to diseases and the maintenance of good immunity depends on nutrition rich food intake in our body. Recently, research focus has been shifted from enhancing the yield towards developing the nutrition rich crop varieties. Researchers are targeting identification of nutraceuticals that play a vital role in maintaining normal physiological functions required for healthy human beings. Different plant foods contain a variety of bioactive compounds such as, phenolic compounds, anthocyanins, dietary fibres, and so on. Presently, our organization has been focused on characterization of vegetables and medicinal plants for identification of nutraceuticals. Recently, we have studied black carrot for its antidiabetic properties where we identified cyanidin 3-xylosyl galactoside is the best potential molecule for inhibiting enzymes involved in glucose metabolism. We have also carried out qualitative profiling of the phenolic compounds in an underutilized aquatic leafy vegetable *Enhydra fluctuans* using ultra performance liquid chromatography. Some of the compounds were found to have antimicrobial and anti-biofilm properties against a human pathogenic bacteria *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The area of nutraceutical research is very important to tackle some of the major life style related disease such as, cancer, obesity, diabetes, cholesterol, arthritis, etc. Therefore, more focused research is needed to develop specific plant foods for better human health and well being.

Cucurbitacin-B Exhibits Anticancer Activity in a Mutated p53 Isoform Harboring Tongue Carcinoma HSC3 Cells

Sukant Garg^{1*}, Sajal Afzal^{1,2}, Jaspreet Kaur Dhanjal¹, Ashish Kaul^{1,2}, He Huifu^{1,3}, Sunil C. Kaul¹, Renu Wadhwa^{1,2}

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Cancer is a syndrome of loss of function and uncontrollable proliferation of an aberrantly mutated cell. Posing as an emerging epidemic, a cancer cell acquires autonomous cell signalling and regulation, resistance against innate immunity and metastasis capability to cause a complete systemic failure and death of the patient. Despite the incredible efforts by the scientist in the past few decades and evolution of the anticancer

therapeutics, a majority are limited by adverse reactions by these molecules and recurrence of the disease. Thus, in order to address these limitations, we have dissected the pharmacodynamics of a number of natural compounds and identified Cucurbitacin B for its role against oral cancers. Cucurbitacin-B (Cuc), a bitter-tasting steroid with cytotoxic properties commonly found in the plants of Cucurbitaceae and Brassicaceae. Celebrated for many medicinal qualities, we for the first time investigated its effects in tongue cancer (HSC3 cells) known to have nearly 50% survival rate. HSC3 cells harbour a mutation in *tp53* viz., phosphorylation deficiency of p53^{Ser46}. 'p53^{Ser46}-to-p53^{Ser46P}' phosphorylation is essential for its interaction with p62 and then later cell apoptosis. By the help of *in vitro* assays and bioinformatics tools, we found that Cuc-treatment in HSC3 cells resulted in the restoration of the p53 activity by considerably improving the p53-p62 interaction and by inhibiting its negative regulators HDM2 and mortalin. We propose further mechanistic and clinical studies with Cucurbitacin-B and for using it against the aggressive oral cancers.

Combinatorial Method for New Materials Design

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The sequencing of combinatorial materials fabrication techniques with high-throughput characterization methods offer a new experimental paradigm to accelerate the discovery and optimization of known and new materials in materials science and engineering field by creating a large number of materials with composition gradient called as Material Library in a single run. In addition, the fundamental understanding of the synthesis route followed by prediction of material compositions with its properties using simulations can save experimental efforts. Based on this, the composition-varied materials fabricated via electrodeposition of binary alloys and multi-component alloys shall be discussed along with its theoretical understanding. Similarly, ab-initio calculations (Density Functional Theory) predicted light weight Ti-based biomaterials followed by its selective synthesis through powder metallurgy route shall also be explained as another case study.

Diboron-catalyzed dehydrative amidation of aromatic carboxylic acids with amines

Dattatraya B. Bagal, Dinesh N. Sawant, Selvam Kaliyamoorthy, Susumu Saito

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Amides are privileged structures found in pharmacological active compounds, agrochemicals, polymers, etc. To construct amide bond, several methods have been developed including direct condensation of carboxylic acids with amines and transition metal based catalysts.¹⁻² The use of coupling reagents are widely accepted as practical alternative in industry, however generation of stoichiometric waste remains an important unsolved challenge. Significant progress has been made in the organoboron compounds since Yamamoto's seminal report on substituted phenylboronic acid catalyzed dehydrative amide condensation of carboxylic acids with amines under azeotropic condition.³ Although these boronic acid-catalysts work fairly well, most of the protocols aimed at the synthesis of aliphatic amide derivatives, in which aromatic carboxylic acids such as benzoic acid derivatives were scarcely examined.

Herein, we report the tetrakis(dimethylamido)diboron and tetrahydroxydiboron as an efficient catalyst for dehydrative amidation of aromatic carboxylic acids with amines under azeotropic reflux condition.⁴ We tested various diboron catalysts and boric acid catalyst for dehydrative amidation, among them tetrakis(dimethylamido)diboron and tetrahydroxydiboron catalysts were identified as excellent catalysts. The developed protocol is very efficient over broad range of substrates bearing electron-withdrawing and -donating substituents at para, meta and ortho position of benzoic acid. Remarkably, these diboron catalysts show much higher catalytic activities than previously reported arylboronic acid catalysts. Furthermore, the developed catalytic system could be used for large-scale synthesis of arylamides.

Scheme 1. Diboron catalyzed direct amidation of aryl carboxylic acids with amine

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Nano-inclusion in thermoelectric AZO thin films

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The conversion of electricity from heat without producing any direct emission of greenhouse gases make thermoelectric (TE) power generation as one of the emerging clean energy technologies. TE materials are quantified by a dimensionless figure of merit $ZT = S^2T\sigma/\kappa$ (where T is a given temperature, S is Seebeck coefficient, and σ is electrical conductivity, and κ is thermal conductivity). These thermoelectric parameters are interconnected by physical laws which makes it challenging to achieve the high performance. However, various approach including nano-engineering can help to find a balance state to reach the goal. TE devices attractive for many applications including automobiles due to the ability of working in dark without any moving part.

ZnO is a wide direct band gap (3.3 eV) n-type semiconductor. ZnO is also a good candidate for thermoelectric applications due to the ability of low-cost, non-toxic, and stable in a wide temperature range. Pure and doped sintered ZnO has been studied as thermoelectric material for space applications, solar-thermal electrical energy production, and so on. Thin films are advantageous over bulks because it allows to engineer the properties of materials at the nanoscale. In bulk oxides like ZnO nano-defects form randomly, and their density and size are quite difficult to control. On the other hand, various thin film deposition techniques allow to control these nano-defects to achieve enhanced thermoelectric performance.

2% Al-doped ZnO (AZO) thin films with Al₂O₃ nano-inclusion were grown by pulsed laser deposition on single crystal and amorphous substrate. Thin films were characterized using state-of-art techniques including XRD, SEM, and TEM. Thermoelectric parameters such as Seebeck coefficient and electrical conductivity were measured in temperature range of 300 K to 600 K. The best result was found for thin film deposited at 400°C on single crystal sapphire substrate as Seebeck coefficient 150 μ V/K, electrical conductivity 40 S/cm and power factor about 90 μ W/m.K². The reduction in the value of thermal conductivity was observed in thin film of AZO+Al₂O₃ than pure AZO. The detailed results will be discussed in the presentation.

Plasma-enhanced CVD growth of vertically oriented carbon nanowalls and its characteristics

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Vertical graphene nanosheets (VGNs) also called carbon nanowalls (CNWs) are a special category of two-dimensional (2D) carbon nanostructure unlike graphene, which grows perpendicular to the substrate. Its unique structural and morphological features such as high aspect ratio, high surface area, sharp edges, and waviness have long been considered for a range of applications from energy storage to sensors¹⁻⁴. CNWs have been leveraged in different applications, for example as potential template material by integrating with other nanostructures like Pt nanoparticles for the fuel cell. The plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PECVD) of CNWs, with the advantage of low processing temperature, is possibly one of the few reliable methodologies to broaden its applications. Although CNWs have been reported to grown on surfaces with no catalyst, its growth characteristics were not fully understood. In this report, the growth of CNWs on different types of substrates like SiO₂/Si and Cu-coated Si substrates using radical-injection PECVD reactor (RI-PECVD) are investigated. The typical vertically oriented nanowall microstructures were obtained in both the substrates with a reasonable growth rate of about 0.1 μm/min as shown in Fig.1. The effects of growth parameters on CNWs microstructure are discussed.

Fig.1 SEM micrographs a) top b) cross-section view of RICVD grown vertical CNWs on insulating surface of SiO₂/Si.

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Functional Substrate for Tuning the Electronic Structure of IrO₂ Nanoparticles for Efficient Water Electrolysis

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Hydrogen stands as a ray of hope in the current scenario of depleting fossil fuels and global pollution. Water electrolysis (WE) using acidic proton exchange membrane water electrolyser (PEMWE) stands as one of the cleanest methods to produce hydrogen from water. Oxygen evolution reaction (OER) that happens at its anode is both thermodynamically and kinetically demanding, hence need an efficient electrocatalysts. IrO₂ is the only known catalyst that can be used in acidic conditions but its high overpotential ~330 mV and cost preclude its future use. In an attempt to reduce the use of high amount of Ir and over potential, several attempts have been made to tune surface area and electronic structure by using nanoparticles (nps) and doping with other metals like Ru, Ni, Co, Pb, Y, Se, Sn, Sr etc or with fluorine. But, the leaching of alloyed metals (durability) is a serious problem. Recently our group has come up with a novel strategy of tuning the electronic structure of IrO₂ nanoparticles (nps) by using electrochemically stable carbon¹ and doped carbon substrates² to change the electronic structure of IrO₂. By using 10 at% nitrogen doped

Fig1: TEM micrograph of IrO₂-N-rGO.

graphene and ultrasmall IrO₂ (Fig 1), **overpotential was reduced to 260-270 mV with very high durability.** Currently we are working on tuning the electron density of catalyst by varying the functional groups on the tailorable conducting polymer substrate to a) establish strong electronic interaction between IrO₂ nanoparticles and substrate for enhanced charge transfer, b) reduce the diffusion and dissolution of IrO₂ over long period of usage (high durability). With this novel strategy the overpotential was reduced to ~260 mV which stands as one of the most promising material for OER application.

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Painless microneedle mimicking female mosquito based on Microneedle production technique

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Our group have been focusing to develop the blood collection device as a part of wearable health care monitoring systems research. Idea was inspired from the blood suction mechanism of female mosquitoes, which can collect blood from human body almost painlessly. Above all, the "world's smallest metal injection needle" created by ultra-fine tube creation technology has been developed with the aim of reducing the burden of daily blood tests for diabetic patients, including the number of reserves. Since it is a wearable device, the mechanism for puncturing a needle, the mechanism for collecting blood, and the mechanism for analyzing blood should be mounted in the limited size within the whilst watch type device, so sensors and actuators based on functional materials, have been used.

Usually in the medical field, the design and creation of medical equipment are done by the company, and there are a few cases where the patient's burden can't be the primary important. Hence it is possible to redesign an application that suits the current usage environment conditions and meets social needs, then patient will be comfortable for taking regular treatments. We are providing solutions for better painless wearable devices to make people life longer.

Fatigue-corrosion behavior of $Zr_{55}Al_{10}Cu_{30}Ni_5$ bulk metallic glass in distilled water

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BMGs are usually said to possess more effective corrosion resistance than its crystalline counterparts. This assumption is based on the presumably more homogeneous passive layer on amorphous metallic materials. Nevertheless, a large spectrum of the fatigue corrosion resistance of BMGs has been described in the literature. Indeed, some BMGs show almost no detriment effect of the corroding environment on the fatigue resistance characteristics in some cases, whereas a strong influence is reported for other ones. Even though corrosion pit formation on the specimens prone to fatigue loading in such environments is reported for BMGs, the characterizations of the pit growth and its transition to fatigue crack in BMGs are still particularly vague. To enhance the comprehension on this critical issue, the fatigue behavior of $Zr_{55}Al_{10}Cu_{30}Ni_5$ (at.%) BMG under four-point loading configuration is investigated in air and in distilled water environments in the present work. Specimens subjected to water environment emphasized the formation of corrosion pits on its tensile surface (see Fig. 1), which induces an early fatigue crack initiation, leading to a decrease of the fatigue resistance compared to the tests operated in air, as depicted in Fig. 2. Experimental results related to the corrosion pit growth and pit-to-crack transition aspects suggest that the fatigue corrosion behavior of $Zr_{55}Al_{10}Cu_{30}Ni_5$ BMG holds strong similarities with its crystalline counterparts.

Fig. 1 Corrosion pit at fatigue crack initiation site

Fig. 2 S-N diagram

Charge density analysis of π -hole interactions of acid dimers in a new co-crystal hydrate of Gallic acid and Pyrazine : application of quantum crystallography

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New polymorphs are of topical interest in crystal engineering, drug discovery and pharmaceutical industries because of the diversity in structure as well as physicochemical properties. Quantum crystallography¹ provides insight into nature of chemical bonding and intermolecular interactions. Gallic acid (Figure 1) is well known to exhibit a complex polymorphic system with five monohydrates, three anhydrides and over 20 solvates.² Recently, donor-acceptor interactions involving π -holes in carboxylic acid dimers were demonstrated in gallic acid system.³

The pK_a difference of the basic pyrazine and acidic proton in gallic acid predicts the formation of a cocrystal as per the Δ pK_a rule assessing the formation of salt or cocrystal. Accordingly, a new hydrate cocrystal was obtained with these two components and characterized by single crystal X-ray diffraction.

The asymmetric unit contains two symmetry independent gallic acid molecules with *syn* COOH group forming an acid dimer, along with half of pyrazine molecule and two water molecules. The acid dimer motifs form donor-acceptor interactions with neighbouring acid dimers. The experimental charge density analysis was carried out using three pronged approach ; multipole model (MP) , Maximum entropy method (MEM) and X-ray wave function refinement (XWR). The signature of the π -hole located at the carboxyl C atom was identified both in static density maps in MP and XWR methods as well as dynamic density in MEM approach (Figure 2) .

Figure 1. Molecular diagram gallic acid indicating feasible torsion angles

Figure 2. (a) Molecular graph indicating C...O interactions from dynamic density in MEM analysis with MP prior (b) 3D static deformation density obtained from MP model (c) and (d) The electrostatic potential mapped on isodensity surface (0.5 eÅ⁻³) from MP and XWR , respectively.

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Development of polyaniline based conducting polymer nano composite for flexible electronics applications

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Recent Advancements in Chemical/Bio Sensors

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In the current technological era, different types of sensors play a significant role and find an indispensable space in almost all the applications. The first decade of the 21st century has been labelled as “Sensor Decade” due to tremendous advances have been made in sensor technology. This talk will begin by presenting brief introduction about chemical/bio sensors and their recent advancements. A few key experimental results about thin film type chemical sensors, ulyrathin flexible nanosheet type sensors will be discussed. various sensing parameters such as sensitivity and selectivity will be presented. All the observed figure of merits of the sensing elements with appropriate sensing mechanisms will be presented. In the end, the designing and development of microfluidics based solid state pH sensor will be touched upon.

Biological and Medical Applications of Raman Spectroscopy

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Biological processes naturally have intricate designs making it difficult to study in detail. In fact, many areas in biology including intracellular dynamics and its biochemistry still largely remain unexplored due primarily to the lack of appropriate tools. Here, I discuss a few examples of how Raman spectroscopy and microscopy aided with multivariate statistics can gain fundamental and otherwise unobtainable biological information to decode some of nature's complex designs.

Single cell Raman imaging: (1) We present for the first-time *in vivo* time lapse Raman imaging, coupled with stable-isotope (¹³C) labelling, to reveal dynamic proteome localization to lipid droplets in single living *Schizosaccharomyces pombe* (*S. pombe*) cells.¹ (2) We further developed a label-free method based on confocal Raman microscopy to visualize distributions of various polysaccharide components of fungal cell and spore wall.² (3) We successfully probed fibril formation and therapeutic targeting of amyloid-like structures in a yeast model of adenine accumulation.³

Probing cellular biochemistry *in vivo*: (1) We show that combination of stable isotope probing (SIP), Raman micro-spectroscopy and multivariate curve resolution (MCR) analysis can serve as a valuable approach in metabolomics research by studying ergosterol biosynthesis in single living fission yeast cells.⁴ (2) We further visualized wax ester fermentation in single *Euglena* cells using Raman microscopy and MCR analysis and obtained chain length-specific information and intracellular distribution images of the produced esters. Accumulated esters in *Euglena* were particularly identified to be myristyl myristate (C28), a wax ester candidate suitable to prepare drop-in jet fuel.⁵ (3) Recently, we are interested in pharmaceutical applications, i.e., imaging drug and its effect at single cell level. I will discuss some results on antifungal agents (unpublished).

Raman diagnostics: (1) The prevalence of eosinophilic esophagitis is increasing. We used Raman spectroscopy as a non-invasive tool to study esophagus of mouse models in which esophagitis is induced artificially by injecting IL-33. We distinguished eosinophil from other types of white blood cells and then successfully developed a Raman spectroscopy based diagnostic technique to detect the existence of eosinophils in esophageal mucous membrane.⁶ (2) Recently, we identified Raman spectral markers and developed a method to objectively discriminate breast cancer and normal mammary epithelial cells in a label-free manner which will be introduced briefly in the meeting (unpublished).

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Multi-Color Regulation of Gold (I) NHC co-ordination Polymer by External Stimuli: via Molecular Aggregates

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Luminescent molecules play an important role in both materials and life science, and their applications as in solid/condensed phase were limited until 2001 due to “aggregation-caused quenching (ACQ)”, In order to overcome these issues arising from the ACQ effect, “aggregation-induced emission (AIE) phenomenon has been come out to the field and played a great impact in academic research as well as in industrial applications of solid-state luminescent molecules, and have thus been extensively investigated. Besides, polymer materials have their own landmark virtues in polymer science such as tunable structure, topology, higher mechanical strength, and easy processability, and thus, if the AIE combines with the polymer which can lead to materials having both the merits. Hence those materials can work in various applications like multi responsive materials.¹ On the other hand, the combination of AIE research with polymer science is less investigated, and many possibilities remain for scientists to explore. The stimuli-responsive, aggregation-induced emission (AIE) with multi-color emission compounds are promising materials for industrial applications. Herein, we report gold (I) N-heterocyclic carbene (NHC) coordination polymer (2) synthesis from its monomer² for the first time, coordination polymer compound shows high thermal stability. In the solid-state, this complex exhibited multi-color emissions in response to their aggregated structure upon exposure to external stimuli. Besides, white color phosphorescence (quantum yield=14%) has been achieved in the crystals even in the air at room temperature originated from the hybrid combination of fluorescence and phosphorescence radiative decay of both singlet and triplet excitons. Also, it exhibits AIE behavior in the solution state. We believe that the multi-color emission, which involves controlling the relative emission intensity is extremely sensitive to their aggregated structure, this aggregated structure can be controlled by applying external stimuli. Our work can provide a new opportunity for the development of practical applications using solid-state luminescent molecules.

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Insights into CRISPR/Cas9 System as a Genome Editing Tool

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Keywords: CRISPR RNA, Cas9, sgRNA, Protospacer adjacent motif, Genome engineering, on-target and off-target activity

CRISPR/Cas9, an RNA-guided endonuclease involved in bacterial defence system has now become a cutting-edge genome editing technology. The ease of programming CRISPR/Cas9 system for recognizing a specific stretch of DNA within billions of nucleotides has paved way for many clinical and industrial applications. The targeting specificity is therefore the key to success for every CRISPR/Cas based experiment. However, its significant off-target activity is a major challenge that still limits its applicability in therapeutics. CRISPR RNA manages to bind to other genomic locations as well that differ from the intended target site by a few nucleotides. In this study, various factors that govern the specificity of CRISPR/Cas9 system to target unique locations in the human genome were studied, and this knowledge was applied to develop a comprehensive resource for designing CRISPR RNAs that possesses high on-target efficiency and minimal or no off-target activity. This work not only reveals some important aspects of target specificity of the CRISPR/Cas system, but also provides novel mechanistic insights into features that are critical for the off-target effects of a designed CRISPR RNA.

An integrative computational systems biology analysis of lung gene expression profiles highlights the differential roles of Tetraspanins Cd151 and Cd9 in lung fibrosis and emphysema

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Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) and Idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis (IPF) are multifactorial disorders that are characterized by distinct clinical and pathological features; however their commonalities and differences are not fully understood. Cd151 and Cd9 are members of the tetraspanin family that is involved in diverse cellular processes, including proliferation, motility and invasion.

We sought to investigate the preventive roles of tetraspanins Cd151 and Cd9 in pulmonary fibrosis and emphysema (a feature of COPD), respectively. Using an integrative systems biology approach, we examined the transcriptomic changes in the lungs of Cd151- and Cd9- knockout (KO) involving functional-enrichment-analysis, pathway-perturbation-analysis and protein-protein-interaction (PPI) network analysis.

Circadian-rhythm, extracellular-matrix (ECM), cell-adhesion and inflammatory responses and associated factors were significantly perturbed by Cd151-deletion. Conversely, cellular-junctions, focal-adhesion, vascular-remodelling and TNF-signalling were deeply influenced by Cd9-deletion. We also pinpointed a “common core” of cellular factors and signalling cascades that underlie the functions of both Cd151 and Cd9 in lung pathology.

Circadian dysregulation that followed Cd151-deletion apparently facilitated a progressive fibrotic lung phenotype. Conversely, the attenuation of TGF- β signalling and activation of TNF-signalling emerged as potentially novel and key modulators of Cd9-deletion-induced emphysema. Our findings offer promising targets for predictive biomarker discovery and for developing novel therapeutic treatments for pulmonary fibrosis and emphysema.

Smart Windows for Energy Savings utilizing Vanadium Dioxide Films with Insulator-Metal Transition

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There is a growing interest for environmentally friendly metal-oxide materials. Vanadium dioxide (VO₂) is known as a phase transition compound which shows insulator-metal transition (IMT) with its structural phase transition (SPT) from low-temperature monoclinic phase (P2₁/c) to high-temperature tetragonal phase (P4₂/mnm) at 68 °C. The abrupt resistivity change over 4 orders of magnitude is realized even in thin films with thickness of less than several tens nm. The reversible and durable IMT has triggered a lot of studies on VO₂ thin films not only for unravelling the physics of phase transition but also for applications to engineering field.

We have been fabricating stoichiometric VO₂ thin films by using reactive magnetron sputtering method. By introducing radio-frequency substrate biasing, we succeeded low temperature growth of stoichiometric VO₂ films on various substrates. As one of promising application, we are trying to fabricate VO₂-coated glasses for smart windows where infrared-light (IR) incidence is automatically controlled to avoid room temperature rise in hot summer.

In the deposition of VO₂ films on glass, we introduced ZnO-buffered layer which is quite effective for succeeding VO₂ crystalline growth. As the result, we successfully obtained oriented growth of VO₂ films with large IMT change. Large change of transmittance for IR concomitant with the IMT enables VO₂-coated glass as smart windows with automatic reduction of IR with temperature rise. As performance index, we realized the solar modulation ability (T_{sol}) of 14.5 % which is world-wide top ranking value, although the luminous transmittance (T_{lum}) of 20% is still rather low. [1, 2]

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Spatial Distribution of Brick Kilns revealed by Remotely Sensed Data: Transfer Learning based Detection around Delhi

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Cities lying in the Indo-Gangetic plains of South Asia have the world's worst anthropogenic air pollution, which is often attributed to urban growth. Brick kilns, facilities for producing fired clay-bricks for construction are often found at peri-urban region of South Asian cities. Although brick kilns are significant air pollutant emitters, their contribution is under-represented in air pollution emission inventories due to unavailability of their distribution. This research overcomes this gap by proposing publicly available remote sensing dataset based approach for mapping brick-kiln locations using object detection and pixel classification. As brick kiln locations are not permanent, an open-dataset based methodology is advantageous for periodically updating their locations. Brick kilns similar to Bull Trench Kilns were identified using the Sentinel-2 imagery around the state of Delhi in India. The unique geometric and spectral features of brick kilns distinguish them from other classes such as built-up, vegetation and fallow-land even in coarse resolution imagery. For object detection, transfer learning was used to overcome the requirement of huge training datasets, while for pixel-classification random forest algorithm was used. The method achieved a recall of 0.72, precision of 0.99 and F1 score of 0.83. Overall 1564 kilns were detected, which are substantially higher than what was reported in an earlier study over the same region. We find that brick kilns are located outside urban areas in proximity to outwardly expanding built-up areas and tall built structures. Duration of brick kiln operation was also estimated by analyzing the time-series of normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) over the brick kiln locations. The brick kiln locations can be further used for updating land-use emission inventories to assess particulate matter and black carbon emissions.

Keywords: deep learning, air pollution, emission, urbanization, remote sensing

Fabrication of highly abundant and cost-effective Fe₂O₃ nanostructures for effective electrocatalytic water splitting

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Hydrogen (H₂) energy has received significant attention due to the scarcity of fossil fuel and their environment impact. The energy density of H₂ is 3 to 4 fold higher than fossil fuels and never pollute the environment by producing CO₂ gas. Among others, electrocatalytic water splitting method has high efficiency, excellent adaptability and flexibility to produce H₂ with high purity. Iron oxide (Fe₂O₃) has great attention for effective water splitting due to its chemical stability, non-toxicity, low-cost, and high abundance than other metal oxides. However, chemical modifications can be performed to improve the efficiency of Fe₂O₃, but the modified electrodes cannot be used for commercial applications due to their high cost and lack of abundance. In this study, chemically unmodified γ -Fe₂O₃ nanowires (NWs) are prepared from highly abundant and low cost Fe plate. The structure and morphology was investigated by spectroscopic/microscopic analyses. The FESEM image of surface strained sample showed highly dense and ordered growth of γ -Fe₂O₃ nanowires on iron plate (Fig. 1(a)). The diameter and length of the nanowire was measured as 397 nm and 1.14 μ m, respectively by TEM analysis. The binding energy, oxidation state and phase transition of Fe₂O₃ was verified by XPS, and the crystal planes and single crystalline structure of the γ -Fe₂O₃ NWs was further confirmed by SAED pattern. Moreover, the fabricated γ -Fe₂O₃ NWs achieved the current density of 10 mA/cm² at 1.88 V vs. RHE as shown in Fig. 1(b). This value is comparable with the reported results where chemical modifications or doping is necessary. The stability measurements of the γ -Fe₂O₃ NWs were monitored up to 3275 sec with the current density of 9.6 mA/cm² at 1.7 V vs. RHE.

Fig. 1. (a) FESEM image and (b) LSV measurement of γ -Fe₂O₃ NWs

Flexible Thermoelectric Material for Energy Applications

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The development of thermoelectric generators for alternate source of energy are currently a major focus as devices capable of supplying an input power (μW to mW) to many sensors, electronic gadgets, and wearable devices in low temperature range around 300 – 400 K [1]. Improvement of *figure of merit*, ZT , of the thermoelectric materials used in such device are very important. Besides, if these materials are flexible [2], the number of applications would be significantly enlarged. Although significant enhancement in ZT of $\text{Ag}_2(\text{S,Se,Te})$ is achieved, but limited to n -type only. Also, it contains the toxic elements, therefore it is not appropriate to make the flexible TE devices which directly used with human body heat. To overcome this issue, modification in electronic structure of flexible Ag_2S is of crucially importance [3]. Therefore, we carried the electronic structure calculations on $\text{Ag}_{2-x}\text{TM}_x\text{S}$ (TM = transition metal element using DFT, and successfully achieved both p and n -type TE property of these material experimentally.

In the present work, we performed the first-principles calculations and also computed the transport coefficients. Secondly, in order to confirm the theoretical results, we synthesized the selected compositions of $\text{Ag}_{2-x}\text{TM}_x\text{S}$, and investigated thermoelectric properties of in the 300-450 K temperature range where only the low temperature phase is obtained. Chemical composition and grain structure analyses were performed using Scanning Electron Microscope-Energy Dispersive X-ray spectroscopy. Heat and electron transport properties were measured on hot-pressed bulk samples. Thermal conductivity measurement was done by using Laser flash analysis; whereas for Seebeck coefficient and electrical resistivity measurement, experimental systems developed in our laboratory were used [4].

The detail results about synthesis, chemical compositions and *figure of merit* obtained in study will be presented in the symposium.

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Abstract

Fabrication of hollow germanium spheres by dropping method

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Keywords: Hollow jet instability, germanium hollow spheres, coaxial nozzle.

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Hollow germanium alloy quasi-spheres of diameters 1 to 2 mm with a relatively smooth inner and outer surface have been produced. The germanium was first melted at around 1273 K and then ejected from a coaxial nozzle into an inert atmosphere by argon gas supplied to the inner nozzle. The falling spheres were cooled by water spray and collected in a bucket. The spheres were somewhat aspherical and had a horn type of structure on the outer surface. The outer diameter varied in the range of 1.3 to 1.8 mm with a wall thickness in the range of 0.2 to 0.5 mm. The frequency of the sphere formation was determined from the videos to be about 133 Hz. Solid silicon spheres are used for spherical silicon solar cells (S_3CS) which have various attractive features. *Hollow* S_3CS promise substantially higher energy conversion efficiency, if their wall thickness can be kept to 0.1 – 0.2 mm and the inner surface can be passivated. Our production of hollow germanium spheres is a significant step towards production of hollow S_3CS with, we hope, higher efficiency and lower material cost than solid S_3CS .

Young Researchers' Session

Comparative corrosion behavior of harmonic structured high entropy Cantor alloy, maraging steel and SUS304L

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Presenter: Debdipta Banik

Abstract

This study deals with corrosion behaviour of the harmonic structured high entropy Cantor alloy ($\text{Fe}_{20}\text{Cr}_{20}\text{Mn}_{20}\text{Ni}_{20}\text{Co}_{20}$). Harmonic structure with grain size of $\sim 3\ \mu\text{m}$ at the shell and $\sim 220\ \mu\text{m}$ at the core was prepared by ball milling followed by spark plasma sintering. Hardness of the harmonic structured cantor alloy was found to be ~ 450 VHN at the core and ~ 550 VHN at the shell. Corrosion behavior of the harmonic structured high entropy alloy has been compared with that of a harmonic structured 304L stainless steel and a maraging steel. The corrosion behavior has been studied with the help of linear and cyclic polarization as well as impedance spectroscopy in freely aerated 3.5 wt% NaCl solution. It has been found that the corrosion resistance for the harmonic structured cantor alloy show higher value than the other steels. There is an enrichment of Cr in the shell region of the harmonic structured cantor alloy and it has been correlated to its corrosion behavior.

Keywords: Harmonic structure, Cantor alloy, Polarisation, Corrosion.

Modeling of Soft Actuators to Grasp Food Items for Lunch Box Packaging

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Food items like Laddu and Burfi are soft objects in terms of compliance. From packaging perspective, handling of such food items is challenging because retaining their shape during the handling process is the key requirement. Due to the complicated behavior, the packaging of such food items is generally performed by humans. Till now, we do not have commercialized grippers to handle such food items. There are grippers made of elastomers to handle packed food items, but their application area is different and are generally used for logistics application. Our main research objective is to design grippers to handle such items and to theoretically analyze their grasping and manipulation mechanics. The design of the grippers basically depends on type of food item and the packaging application. The targeted application areas of our research are lunch (Bento) box packaging and raw food handling. We use silicone rubbers to fabricate the grippers as they are highly compliant material and are best suited for such applications. Due to the elastomeric behavior, the soft grippers possess large deformation even when subjected to lower magnitudes of forces. Because of their highly compliant nature, the behavior of these grippers is very difficult to predict using previously developed theories for stiffer structures.

We developed an analytical model for a pleated geometry type fluidic elastomer actuator (FEA) that estimates both deformation and force characteristics of the actuator. For application, the model is implemented on a three-finger gripper to estimate the air pressure required for a stable grasp of different objects and is experimentally validated. The theoretical model is very efficient in terms of computation time when compared to the finite element method (FEM) model of the actuator. The developed model is physically more general compared to previously developed models of the FEA, because it considers external contact.

An Efficient Approach to Zero Crossing Detection Based on Opto-coupler

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Abstract: Zero crossing detection is the most common method for measuring the frequency or the period of a periodic signal. This study presents a comparative study of various zero-crossing detector techniques. The accuracy of measuring zero crossings for synchronizing power system control and instrumentation requires a diverse approach to minimize phase-detection errors from signals corrupted with noise and extraneous signals. An approach to detect zero crossings with the use of an opto-coupler is described in this study. The issues related to the previous approaches have been discussed, along with their pros and cons. The performance analysis is done using MATLAB based simulations. The method can be easily implemented in low-cost devices and is computationally very efficient.

Cellulose Nanofiber Reinforced Starch Film With High Mechanical Strength And Durability In Water

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Abstract:

Single-use plastics become a post-consumer waste and create a big problem for the society and environment. Polysaccharides are the potential replacement of single-use plastics, however, lack of mechanical strength and water durability restrict their applications. Starch and cellulose are ubiquitous biomass in nature, but packaging film cast with only starch or cellulose has poor wet strength and collapse in water. TEMPO oxidation of cellulose results in a highly fibrillated cellulose nanofiber (TCNF). The self-standing film of TCNF is flexible and transparent with a high tensile modulus (6-7 GPa), however, its inferior wet strength and high swelling network restrain packaging applications.

We prepared cellulose nanofiber reinforced starch film, which had adequate strength and stability in water. TCNF was combined with three different types of modified tapioca starch: hydroxypropyl starch (HPS), acetyl starch (AS) and acetyl oxidized starch (AOS), in a 3:2 weight ratio. The TCNF/starch suspension subsequently converted into a film by solution casting. It was demonstrated that the TCNF/starch film reduced its swelling in water and enhanced mechanical strength in wet conditions. These results suggest that hemiacetal bonding between TCNF and starch elevated the water durability and strength of the film. Minimum swelling and highest wet tensile modulus (7 MPa) was observed in TCNF/HPS film, indicating that TCNF/HPS film had dense hemiacetal bonding compare to the other starch blended films. Dried TCNF/HPS film had adequate mechanical strength (120 MPa) and the transparency was high enough to replace the existing plastic. Recently, the composite film has been found to show good biodegradability in marine conditions. Therefore, the TCNF reinforced HPS film opens the research for the next generation renewable, biodegradable, water-durable high performance - green packaging film.

Graphical abstract

Monitoring human behavior using pose estimation

RATHORE Aditya Singh, M2
Emergent Systems Laboratory
November 13, 2020

1 Introduction

Pose estimation in general, is a skeletal representation of the orientation of a person in a graphical format. These are a set of coordinates taken from an image of a person. Each coordinate in the skeleton is known as a part (or a joint, or a key-point). A valid connection between two parts is known as a pair (or a limb). Note that, not all part combinations give rise to valid pairs.

The human activity monitoring technology is one of the most important technologies for ambient assisted living, surveillance-based security, sport and fitness activities and healthcare of elderly people. The human monitoring is performed in two steps: the acquisition of body coordinates and the classification of activities being performed.

2 Research Topic

Problem:

Traditional monitoring Systems only detect human presence and/or classify the current human action. There is no application that can predict the different action types when given current poses such as eating or sleeping. Another problem with traditional systems is that they are unable to do scene recognition using pose estimation information.

Solution:

I propose an algorithm for smart surveillance system for humans using the following below features:

1. Human Pose Coordinates
2. Action class information
3. Position of the subject
4. Time of action

2.1 Human Pose Coordinates: These will be achieved using the Open Pose deep learning algorithm.

OpenPose:

OpenPose is one of the most popular bottom-up approaches for multi-person human pose estimation. It first detects parts (keypoints) belonging to every person in the image, followed by assigning parts to distinct individuals.

2.2 Action class information: This information is achieved by the use of inflated 3D convolutional

neural networks with inception v1 as the underlying architecture. This can be done by starting with a 2D architecture, and inflating all the filters and pooling kernels – endowing them with an additional temporal dimension. Filters are typically square and we just make them cubic – $N \times N$ filters become $N \times N \times N$.

2.3 3D World position of the subject: This information will give the coordinates of the subject in the 3D plane. The x and y coordinates are mapped towards the head point of the subject. This head point is obtained through the pose estimation algorithm. The z coordinates corresponds to the depth information for the head point pixel that is obtained by the depth data. This head position is then de-projected to world coordinates using the camera intrinsic and extrinsic values.

2.4 Time of action: It is the time at which a certain detection was made.

Figure 1: Model output showing classification, pose estimation and 3d World position of the subject.

Abstract

Three-arm Aerial Manipulator System (TAMS) for UAVs to Realize Multiple Tasks

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Keywords: Aerial manipulation, UAVs, multitask robots

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The use of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) is becoming progressively popular in recent years. Due to their high speed, high portability and ability to operate in 3D space, small size UAVs are highly desirable for time sensitive, complex observation or manipulation tasks. Those tasks can occur in complex deployment scenarios such as rescue operations or disaster relief.

Our work describes the concept, design and realization of a novel manipulator system for a multirotor aerial robot. The proposed manipulator system consists of three robotic arms attached to a multirotor frame. To overcome the limited payload capabilities in multirotor aerial platforms, the same set of on-board manipulators are used to realize various tasks, primarily the manipulation or grasping of objects of various sizes. Along with a vision and on-board processing system can intelligently perform multiple tasks using the same set of hardware. Furthermore, they can provide aid in complex navigation tasks by doing physical, contact based obstacle avoidance and are able to act as adaptive landing gear in uneven terrain. The proposal is supported with the successful demonstration of these tasks using the aerial multi manipulator system in an outdoor environment.

Interface analysis of γ -CuI and β -Ga₂O₃ heterojunction by temperature dependent device characteristics

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Abstract:

Herein, we report on the temperature dependent device characteristics of the p-type γ -copper iodide (γ -CuI)/n-type β -gallium oxide (β -Ga₂O₃) heterojunction and thereby revealing the interface properties. A predominantly (111) oriented cubic γ -CuI phase was deposited on (020) oriented β -Ga₂O₃ substrate by evaporation technique. The fabricated γ -CuI/ β -Ga₂O₃ heterojunction showed excellent diode characteristics with low series resistance, excellent rectification, and low reverse saturation current in presence of large barrier height (0.632 eV) at room temperature (298K). The temperature dependent device characteristics were studied in the temperature range of 273-473K to investigate the heterojunction interface. With the increase in temperature a gradual decrease in ideality factor and increase in barrier height was observed, signifying the barrier inhomogeneity at the heterojunction interface. Again, electrical analysis showed small hysteresis effect for reverse saturation current, without no hysteresis effect for forward bias current. The absence of large electrical hysteresis indicates low interface states for the fabricated γ -CuI/ β -Ga₂O₃ heterojunction. It was also observed that applying a temperature as high as 473K, the rectification behavior and saturation current was not affected. This study revealed the excellent diode characteristics with large built-in field for the γ -CuI and β -Ga₂O₃ wide band gap semiconductor heterojunction for various device applications.

Electrochemical Performance of High Phosphorus Pig Iron as Sacrificial Anode for Cathodic Protection of Steel in Seawater

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Abstract

Cathodic protection (CP) is the widely used method to protect subsea structures, underground pipelines and reinforced concrete structures. Zinc and aluminium based sacrificial anodes are commonly used to protect steel structures in the marine environment due to their large current capacity and high efficiency. Al-based sacrificial anodes are more preferred over zinc anodes due to their low density and high current capacity. However, these anodes are highly prone to stress corrosion cracking due to high negative reduction potential than that of the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER). This necessitates the development of an alternate material to be used as a sacrificial anode in the marine environment.

The present work investigates the performance of pig iron with three different phosphorus content (1.5%P, 3.5%P and 8.0%P) as sacrificial anode to protect mild steel in artificial seawater. Microstructural observation has revealed the presence of inhomogeneous distribution of phosphorus in the matrix of iron along with non-metallic inclusions. These phases are responsible for the unstable passive layer and formation of soluble iron phosphate on the surface of iron. Based on the potentiodynamic polarization study, 3.5% phosphorus pig iron has shown greater negative corrosion potential and higher corrosion current density as compared to the mild steel. The polarization resistance of all the pig iron samples are also much lower than that of the mild steel. The anode capacity and closed-circuit potential (CCP) of all the pig iron samples have been evaluated based on TM0190 as recommended by NACE standards. Industrial trials have also been performed for all the pig iron samples in the artificial seawater environment where corrosion rate, open circuit potential (OCP) and CCP have been monitored for a period of 252 days. The phase identification of the corrosion products on the surface of the pig iron and the mild steel samples after potentiodynamic polarization and immersion tests have been characterized with the help of the Raman spectroscopy. The presence of soluble iron phosphate hydrate ($\text{FePO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and inhomogeneous microstructure have been found to be conducive to improve the electrochemical performance of the pig iron anode. Finally, a mechanism has been proposed to understand the corrosion mechanism and role of entrapped inclusions of pig iron samples during immersed conditions.

Keywords: Sacrificial anode; Corrosion; Artificial seawater; Anode capacity.

Fucoxanthin Exerts Anti-stress Activities and is suitable for Recruitment for the Improvement of the Quality of Life

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Stress is a physiological response to a pathological stimulus. Its prolonged exposure may trigger the onset of complications such as accelerated aging, neurodegenerative diseases and cancer. With expanding average lifespan and worsening environmental

conditions, these are unlikely to be subtle. Because of their complexity and discrete signs in the early stages, they are diagnosed mostly at an advanced stage, posing a hurdle for clinicians. Thus, investigation into its preventive interventions is warranted. We investigated the anti-stress activities by the non-toxic doses of fucoxanthin, a marine carotenoid abundantly found in *Undaria pinnatifida* (wakame) using a variety of cell and stress-based assays. Response of cultured mammalian cells to a variety of stresses, and their prevention was investigated. In the anti-stress model, fucoxanthin treatment protected the skin-derived G361 and MeWo cells against the OAG- and epinephrine-derived melanogenesis. In the brain derived cell model, it protected the astrocytic C6 cells against heavy metal, heat and UV radiation stresses via activation of the DNA damage repairing MRN complex and promoted their re-differentiation into a healthy cell phenotype via increase in a cascade of cell-specific proteins. In cancer cell metastasis models, fucoxanthin treatment reduced the migration of the cancer cells. These mechanisms were found to revolve around mortalin inhibition and antioxidant mechanisms. Our results suggest that a low dose supplementation of Fucoxanthin may provide protection against a variety of stress-complications and hence aid to an increase in the quality of life.

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Novel caffeic acid phenethyl ester-mortalin antibody nanoparticles offer enhanced selective cytotoxicity to cancer cells

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Key words: CAPE; Mortalin, Internalizing antibody, Nanoparticles, Enhanced drug delivery, Cancer therapy.

Caffeic acid phenethyl ester (CAPE) is a key bioactive ingredient of honeybee propolis and claimed to have anticancer activity. Since mortalin, a hsp70 chaperone, is enriched in cancer cell surface, we recruited a unique cell internalizing anti-mortalin antibody (MotAb) to generate mortalin-targeting CAPE nanoparticles (CAPE-MotAb). Biophysical and biomolecular analyses revealed an enhanced anticancer activity of CAPE-MotAb both in *in vitro* and *in vivo* assays. We demonstrate that CAPE-MotAb cause stronger dose-dependent growth arrest/apoptosis of cancer cells through downregulation of Cyclin D1-CDK4, phospho-Rb, PARP-1 and anti-apoptotic protein Bcl2. Concomitantly, significant increase in the expression of p53, p21^{WAF1} and caspase cleavage was obtained in CAPE-MotAb treated cells. We also demonstrate that CAPE-MotAb caused remarkably enhanced the downregulation of proteins critically involved in cell migration. *In vivo* tumor growth assays for subcutaneous xenografts in nude mice also revealed a significantly enhanced suppression of tumor growth in the treated group suggesting that these novel CAPE-MotAb nanoparticles may serve as a potent anticancer nanomedicine.

Withaferin A and CAPE Combination for Treatment for Aggressive Cancers

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Keywords: Anticancer, CAPE, Withaferin A, p53-mortalin, apoptosis, metastasis

Aggressive cancers are defined by uncontrolled extremely rapid proliferation and migration of cancer cells from the primary to secondary sites in the body. Withaferin A (Wi-A) is a withanolide derived from Ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*), and CAPE (Caffeic Acid Phenethyl Ester) is an active compound from New Zealand honeybee propolis. Both of these natural compounds were shown to have anticancer activities. We generated a low dose combination of Wi-A and CAPE and investigated its effect on cervical carcinoma. We found that similar to Wi-A and CAPE, the combination was able to abrogate mortalin-p53 interaction, resulting in nuclear translocation and reactivation of p53 function yielding apoptosis in cancer cells. Furthermore, the combination caused inactivation of poly ADP-ribose polymerase 1 (PARP1); a key regulator of DNA repair yielding growth arrest in cancer cells. We next examined the effect of nontoxic, ultra-low doses of Wi-A, CAPE and combination on migration of cancer cells and found that in addition to the better anti-proliferation activity, the combination was effective in delaying the migration of the cancer cells through inactivation of Wnt- β Catenin signaling and hence is predicted to be useful for treatment of metastatic cancers.

Stem Extract of *Cinnamomum zeylanicum* Cause Cytotoxicity in the Osteosarcoma Cells

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Keywords: Cinnamon, growth arrest, mortalin, apoptosis, DNA damage, pATR.

Cancer is a disease, in which the abnormally mutated cells begin to divide uncontrollably, and often attack the surrounding tissues. Natural compounds have recently attracted attention due to their safety and economic aspects. We have earlier identified anticancer, anti-stress and anti-aging activities in *Withania somnifera*, *Helicteres angustifolia* and honeybee propolis using human cultured normal and cancer cells. A variety of extracts from these herbs were tested in cell-based assays. In this study, we have used Cinnamon extracts prepared from *Cinnamomum zeylanicum* obtained from St. Leonards on-Sea Estate, Karandeniya, Sri Lanka and evaluated their anticancer activity along with their molecular analyses. Cinnamon bark extracts were found to be safe for both cancer and normal cells (in the range of 0.01-1.0%, for at least 4 weeks). On the other hand, its stem extracts prepared in a specific way (established on our laboratory) showed selective cytotoxicity in osteosarcoma cells. We investigated the molecular mechanism of anticancer activity and found that activation of p53 and pRB tumor suppressor activities in cancer cell specific manner.

Lipoic Acid Enantiomers Exert Hypoxia and Anti-stress Activity in Mammalian Cells and Cause Lifespan Extension in Human Lung Fibroblasts

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Keywords: Natural compound, senescence, stress, fibroblasts, autophagy, hypoxia, aging.

Stress is the reaction of the living cells to an environmental stimulus that is perceived to be undesirable. At the molecular level, it is marked by a shift of cell signaling pathways from homeostasis to recovery mechanisms. These cellular shifts may be recorded and investigated using a variety of cell-based assays. These stress-mediated shifts in advanced and/or acute stages are responsible for the onset of various stress-related diseases, such as cancer, accelerated aging and neurodegeneration. In order to address these, a number of molecular therapies are devised. We identified such activities with their molecular mechanisms in the alpha-lipoic acid (ALA) enantiomers, R-(+)-ALA and S(-)-ALA. While R-(+)-ALA is a natural essential cofactor of the mitochondrial-based cell oxidative machinery, S(-)-ALA is its optical isomer by-product. We subjected the non-toxic doses of these compounds to the rat glioma C6 cells, and found that they protected the cells against the heavy metal (sodium (meta)arsenite), heat and oxidative (UV and hydrogen peroxide) stresses via an accelerated hypoxia signaling and autophagy. Since flaws in these mechanisms are known to result in rapid aging and cyto-degeneration, we supplemented the healthy human lung fibroblasts with R-(+)-ALA and S(-)-ALA. Our results suggest that R-(+)-ALA and S(-)-ALA may cause an extension of the lifespan of these cells (R>S), advocating for further studies for their role as anti-aging health supplements.

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A multi-target novel small molecule as an alternative therapeutic strategy for the Luminal-A breast cancers

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Keywords: synthetic small molecule; p53-mortalin interaction; abrogation; Luminal-A breast cancer.

Abstract: Mortalin is an oncogenic member of the Hsp70 family of proteins that physically binds to the p53 tumour suppressor protein sequestering it in the cytoplasm. Hence, a library of small molecules was screened to identify compounds that have potential to abrogate mortalin-p53 interaction, re-translocate p53 to the nucleus, and reactivate its function. We identified a novel synthetic small molecule (AIST code: CL49) that showed such potentials. In order to test its potentials as an anticancer compound, we undertook extensive bioinformatics and experimental analyses that revealed CL49 as a novel small molecule that could abrogate mortalin-p53 binding causing reactivation of p53 function. and yielding growth arrest or apoptosis in cancer cells with wild type but inactive p53 protein. Cells treated with CL49 showed activated apoptosis (mediated by increase in *Bax* and *Puma*) and cell cycle arrest (mediated by increase in *p21^{WAF1}* protein). Furthermore, CL49 caused anomalies in the DNA damage repair machinery that were marked by the increase in cleaved PARP1 and PAR polymer in different cancer cell lines. The data suggested that CL49 has unique p53-dependant and independent anti-cancer activities that may be recruited of treatment of Luminal-A breast cancers.

Effect of Ashwagandha withanolides (withanone and withaferin-A) on muscle cell differentiation

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Key words: Ashwagandha, myoblast, muscle differentiation, protein aggregation, autophagy

Withania somnifera (Ashwagandha) is commonly used in Indian traditional medicine, Ayurveda and is believed to have a variety of health promoting effects. Molecular mechanisms and pathways underlying these effects have not yet been sufficiently explored. Skeletal muscle is the largest tissue of the human body and plays an important role in facilitating motion and modulating metabolite levels. In this study, we investigated the effect of Ashwagandha extract and its major withanolides (Withaferin A & Withanone) on muscle cell differentiation using C2C12 myoblasts. We have found that Withaferin A & Withanone, and Ashwagandha extracts possessing different ratios of these active ingredients have different effects on differentiation of C2C12. Withanone and Withanone-rich extracts caused stronger differentiation of myoblasts to myotubes, de-aggregation of heat and metal stress induced aggregated proteins and activation of autophagy pathways. These results demonstrate potential of Ashwagandha withanolides for management of muscle repair and activity.

Molecular Link between Cancer and Hyperglycemia- Intervention by Natural Compounds

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Disruption of cellular metabolism occurs often with carcinogenesis. Glucose metabolism becomes a concern as it provides energy for the cancer cell growth and proliferation. It is known that people with diabetes have a high incidence of certain cancer types. A high amount of glucose contributes to the endogenous formation of advanced glycation end products (AGEs), which leads to deregulation of several signaling pathways that in turn promote cancer. Hyperglycemia has also been associated with critical steps of the cancer metastasis. c-Myc, p53, and hypoxia-inducible factor (HIF)-1 α are involved in regulation of glucose metabolism. Natural compounds are often recommended and used in traditional home medicine for their potent anticancer activity and positive impact on glucose levels. In this presentation, we will summarize signaling pathways as potential targets of natural compounds in management of cancer and hyperglycemic states. Molecular link in the signaling pathways involved in cancer and diabetes will be discussed.

Comparative Analysis of Sand Indices for Monitoring of Soiling on Solar Farms in Arid Environments

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The soiling of solar panels from dry deposition affects the overall efficiency of power output from solar power plants. This study focuses on the detection and monitoring of sand deposition (wind-blown dust) on photovoltaic (PV) solar panels in arid regions using multitemporal remote sensing data. The study was conducted in Bhadla solar park of Rajasthan, India which receives numerous sandstorms every year, carried by westerly and north-westerly winds. In this study we used Google Earth Engine (GEE), a cloud based platform for image processing because of its exceptional capability and quick results reproduction. The aim of the study was to detect soiling and identify the areas of the farm most affected by it. Pre processed optical imageries dataset in the Earth Engine were used for the generation of various sand indices such as the normalized differential sand index (NDSI), the ratio normalized differential soil index (RNDSI), and the dry bare soil index (DBSI). Apart from that, Land surface temperature (LST) derived from Landsat 8 thermal bands were also used to correlate its results with sand indices and to observe the pattern of sand accumulation in the target region. Additionally, high-resolution PlanetScope images were procured to quantitatively validate the sand indices. Our study suggests that the use of freely available satellite data with semiautomated processing on GEE can be a useful alternative to manual methods. The developed method can provide near real-time monitoring of soiling on PV panels cost-effectively. This study concludes that the DBSI method has a comparatively higher potential (89.6% Accuracy, 0.77 Kappa) in the detection of sand deposition on PV panels as compared to other indices. The findings of this study can be useful to solar energy companies in the development of an operational plan for the cleaning of PV panels regularly.

Monitoring of Ravines and gully erosion using remote sensing and GIS in last few decades: Review

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Ravines are the most extreme type of land degradation caused by water due to its associated environmental, ecological, social and economic hazard. It is the complex network of several of gullies, threatened the whole ecosystem and sustainability of many rural and urban community. Gullies are the continuous depression on the sloping land surface because of soil displacement by over-flow of water and also by gravitational force on land. This system makes land totally unproductive and destroy socio-economic structure of local area associated with that. Most of the world's cultivated lands are affected by land degradation. Gully erosion and Ravines are the biggest evidence of soil degradation. As it is very complex ecological system its sustainable reclamation is very important with the help of advance technological methods like remote sensing and GIS. The capability of remote sensing to provide the actual spatial and homogenous data of earth with regular revisit potential is significantly efficient for gully erosion assessment. Its been almost 50 years of Remote sensing in field of environmental monitoring but in last two decades it has been evolved with various advancement and complexity. In this presentation we will review the use of remote sensing and GIS in ravines and gully erosion monitoring and mapping done in last few decades with especial attention on the evolution and decadal changes happen in methodologies. The limitation and pros and cons of some parameter will be also discussed for the future projects.

Synergistic Use of Aerial and Ground Survey Techniques for Archaeological Site Mapping

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The study demonstrated mapping workflow using commercial grade Unmanned Aerial Vehicle System (UAVs), low-cost Post-Processing Kinematics (PPK) Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) and Open Source softwares for archaeological sites mapping. The study areas are ancient burial tomb and ancient pottery site dated to the 1st century located in Batken State, Kyrgyzstan in Central Asia. Previous explorations and excavation activities were conducted in the sites found mummified bodies including valuable artifacts. Digital documentation of the sites are important for the archaeologist and scientist who studying the sites since the study area are subjected to risk of slope erosions and overtime land use and land cover changes. The Structure from Motion (SfM) aerial UAV photogrammetry produces ultra-high resolution 2D and 3D outputs of Digital Surface Model (DSM), Point Clouds and Orthomosaic Aerial Photos. Meanwhile GNSS ground survey outputs were medium resolution ground truth Digital Terrain Model (DTM) and generated contours. The outputs were combined to produce maps of the study sites which presents constructed topographical details also conditions of the sites. Such information are very useful in the quest of studying also protection and preserving the ancient historical treasures. The study also was a good skills building and useful experience excersice for the local scientist and archaeologist who interested with synergistic applications of aerial and ground survey techniques where they can replicate for mapping other archaeological sites in the area.

Evaluation of Anticancer Activities in Medicinal Mushroom (*Cordyceps militaris*) Grown on Fluorinated Medium

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Key words: *Cordyceps militaris*, fluorine, anticancer.

Cordyceps militaris (CM), a traditional Chinese insect-born fungus, has been long used as alternative medicine and is popular for antimicrobial, antioxidant, and hyperglycaemic activities. Fluorine, due to its small size and strong electron-withdrawing property, is widely applied in medicinal chemistry to improve potency and permeability of drugs. We anticipated that CM culture in the fluorine-supplemented medium may generate the strains with enriched molecular benefits of fluorine. We examined the effects of NH₄F- and KF-supplemented medium on CM cultivation and its properties by harvesting CM fruit body. The water extracts from CM fruit body were used to evaluate their anticancer effect using cell viability assays in human lung carcinoma (A549). Compared with the extracts prepared from CM raised in normal medium, extracts prepared from CM raised in NH₄F- and KF-supplemented medium showed stronger cytotoxicity to A549. We examined molecular markers of growth arrest and apoptosis and found that such a phenotypic change was supported by a stronger activation of growth arrest and apoptosis signalling. Furthermore, extracts obtained from CM raised in NH₄F- and KF-supplemented medium caused inhibition of cell migration that was mediated by downregulation of MMP-2. These results demonstrated that extracts obtained from CM raised in NH₄F- and KF-supplemented medium may serve as stronger anticancer amalgams.

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Development of vitamin D₃ and its analogs for prevention and treatment of osteoporosis and cancer

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Abstract

1 α , 25-dihydroxyvitamin D₃ (1 α , 25(OH)₂D₃) is an active form of vitamin D₃ which is traditionally known to regulate the bone metabolism and calcium homeostasis. Accumulating evidences also suggested that 1 α , 25(OH)₂D₃ possesses many anti-cancer functions. A mitochondrial enzyme CYP24A1 (cytochrome P450 family 24 subfamily A member 1) is a key enzyme which catalytic degrades the vitamin D₃ level in blood which leads the various types of diseases such as osteoporosis and cancer. Therefore, developing the vitamin D₃ derivatives that can generate the high resistance against CYP24A1-based degradation has been considered as a promising therapeutic approach so far for osteoporosis and cancer treatment^{1 & 2}.

With this aim to develop the most potent vitamin D₃ analogs-based drugs for the treatment of osteoporosis and cancer, we synthesized various types of vitamin D₃ analogs with structures combining “19-demethylenation” and “C2 α -modification” with different hydrocarbon moieties. We evaluated their resistance against CYP24A1-based degradation in enzymatic assay and measured their metabolic conversion % by HPLC system. In addition, we tested their binding with vitamin D receptor (VDR) by split luciferase assay and the anti-proliferative functions in cancer cells. Interestingly, some analogs showed a remarkable resistance against CYP24A1 and high binding affinity with VDR. Moreover, these analogs in cell-viability/cytotoxic-based assays were also identified with the high anti-proliferative functions. In this symposium, we will describe the metabolism of vitamin D₃ and its-derivatives by CYP24A1 and its implication in cancer in an attempt to develop more potent CYP24A1-resistant vitamin D₃ analogs with low hypercalcemic effects for osteoporosis and cancer treatment.

Keywords: Active form of vitamin D₃, CYP24A1, vitamin D₃ analogs

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Development of recombinant adenoviral vectors for the treatment of rickets

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Recently, we successfully generated vitamin D 1 α -hydroxylase (CYP27B1)-deficient rats, an animal model of type I rickets, and vitamin D receptor (VDR)-deficient rats, an animal model of type II rickets using genome-editing methods with CRISPR/Cas9 system to reveal molecular mechanism of multiple vitamin D actions (1).

Next, we attempt to develop gene therapy methods for type I and type II rickets using a recombinant adenoviral vector harboring rat CYP27B1 cDNA or rat VDR cDNA. Our final goal is a gene therapy using the adenoviral vectors harboring Cas9 or Cas9 nickase with guide RNAs and donor DNAs. It is noted that there are neither drugs nor treatments for alopecia caused by type II rickets.

The recombinant adenoviral vectors harboring rat CYP27B1 cDNA or rat VDR cDNA under the control of the EF1 α promoter was successfully constructed according to COS-TPC (cosmid-terminal protein complex) method, and the resultant adenoviral vectors were propagated in HEK293 cells whose genome contain E1 region of the adenovirus type 5. Then, each of the recombinant adenoviral vectors was infected to human prostate-derived PZ-HPV-7 cells to confirm the functional expression of CYP27B1 or VDR. As a next step, we plan to inject the recombinant adenoviral vectors into CYP27B1-deficient rats or VDR-deficient rats via the tail vein to treat rickets.

(1) Nishikawa M. *et al.*, Generation of novel genetically modified rats to reveal the molecular mechanisms of vitamin D actions. *Sci Rep.* 10 (1):5677 (2020)

Analysis of the effects of vitamin D and calcium on the female reproductive functions among genetically modified rats

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Vitamin D is an important food factor for bone health, whose deficiency and dysfunction cause bone diseases such as rickets and osteoporosis. It has also been reported that vitamin D is involved in fertility. In fact, several studies have demonstrated that the rickets mouse models such as *Cyp27b1*-KO and *Vdr*-KO showed poor development of female reproductive organs and the null mutant mice were infertile. However, detailed mechanism has not been clarified. In this study, the effects of vitamin D and calcium on female reproductive functions were examined by using three genetically modified (GM) rats which shows the rickets symptoms.

Three types of GM rats were generated by CRISPR/Cas9 system. ① *Cyp27b1*-KO rats show significantly decreased plasma 1,25D3 because of the non-functional enzyme which catalyzing 1 α -hydroxylation of 25-hydroxyvitamin D3. ② *Vdr* (R270L) rats have the mutant *Vdr* whose binding affinity towards 1,25D3 is significantly decreased. ③ *Vdr*-KO rats have no genomic action of 1,25D3 or 25D3 via *Vdr*.

Reproductive efficiency in homozygotes was quite low in the three types of GM rats as compared with wild-type rats. Hypoplasia of the reproductive organs including ovary and uterus was observed in all GM rats and it was the most severe in *Cyp27b1*-KO rats. Estrous cycle was slightly disrupted in GM rats. In *Cyp27b1*-KO and *Vdr* (R270L) rats, 25D3 diet fully restored their reproductive efficiency and the number of offspring per dam was also equivalent to that of wild type. Bleeding under the calcium rescue diet also enabled *Vdr*-KO rats to generate their offspring. These results suggest that *Vdr*-dependent actions of 1,25D3 and 25D3 are not essential for reproduction, and the normal serum Ca level may be essential.

Photocatalytic Marimo balls (P-Marimo) based on plasmonic titanium nitride and chromium-doped titanium dioxide for eco-friendly water treatment

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Release of industrial untreated wastewater creates hazardous impact on the environment [1]. In this regard, development of environment friendly catalyst is of paramount importance. When titanium nitride (TiN) is attached to a semiconducting photocatalyst, photo-excited carriers in the TiN can be injected into the semiconductor, thus enhancing the photocatalytic activity [2].

Figure 1. Photocatalytic marimo balls (P-Marimo) immobilized with plasmonic TiN/SiO₂/Cr-TiO₂. Here, we report a highly efficient and reusable plasmonic TiN/SiO₂/Cr-TiO₂ (TSCT) core-shell photocatalyst structure which is composed of SiO₂ cladded plasmonic TiN nanoparticles (NPs) decorated with Cr doped TiO₂ NPs for the removal of organic contaminant from water. The TiN NPs served as the main light absorbing component with superior visible light absorption along with Cr-TiO₂ NPs. We step further for an efficient structural design by adopting calcium alginate beads as transparent scaffold for supporting our TSCT. Our newly proposed catalyst (P-Marimo beads) exhibit floatable nature on the water surface and realizes easy handling as well as excellent reusability with high catalytic activity for multipurpose water purification.

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